

To What Extent Can We Detect Microplastics with NIR Imaging?

José Manuel Amigo^{1,2*}, Reaha Goyetche²

¹IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, Plaza Euskadi 5, 48009 Bilbao, Spain

²IBeA, Department of Analytical Chemistry, University of the Basque Country, 48940 Leioa, Spain

Near-infrared hyperspectral imaging (NIR-HSI) is seen as a plausible analytical choice to detect diverse microplastics in natural samples in real-time (bearing in mind that a microplastic size range is from 1000 to 0.1 microns). Undoubtedly, the ability to collect precise spectral information of a surface at a suitable spatial level, together with the appropriate chemometric methods, makes NIR-HSI a suitable methodology to create reliable analytical methodologies. Nevertheless, there are an important number of analytical concerns that require a deep understanding of the interactions between NIR radiation, microplastics, and the matrices in which microplastics are located. These include spatial resolution and the spectral resolution of the camera affecting the limit of detection of the methodology, the presence of the plausible interference, the surface roughness, the speed of the measurement, and the generation of proper databases and their usage.

This presentation will discuss the aforementioned points through a critical lens to face different issues and suggest plausible solutions. To do so, several controlled simulations of real scenarios will be studied by using standardized beach sand and microparticles of common plastics (polypropylene and polystyrene) with different particle sizes (ranging from 2000 to 20 microns). The measurements will be done with a bench-top push-broom NIR-HSI equipment working in the range of 1000–1600 nm at different spatial resolutions (from 100 to 25 microns). Topics addressed and discussed will include the minimum spatial and spectral resolution required to detect the microplastics (spatial and spectral multivariate limit of detection with different particle sizes and interferences) and the feasibility/reliability of creating databases to use them.

Keywords: NIR imaging, microplastics, limit of detection, classification, database, cluttering methods